

Appendix B. Grounded Theory Codebook

S. No	Indicative Quotes	First Order Categories	Second Order Categories	Overarching Themes
1.	“ChatGPT’s predisposition to abstraction extends to its recommendations across various consumer decision scenarios. For example, the experiments demonstrate that ChatGPT primarily favours product and pricing recommendations consistent with high-level construals. Consequently, ChatGPT’s solutions lead to different outcomes for consumer recommendations compared to the literature on how consumers make decisions...” (Kirshner, 2024, p. 10)	AI Recommendation Influence on Decision Quality	AI recommendations’ effect on consumers’ decisions	Information Search and AI Recommendation
2.	“Considering implications for online stores, this work outlines the effects of a recommendation agent based on a novel preference relaxation technique, and shows its positive effects on consumer decision-making performance.” (Dabrowski & Acton, 2013, p. 5560)	AI Recommendation Influence on Decision Quality	AI recommendations’ effect on consumers’ decisions	Information Search and AI Recommendation
3.	“In sum, AI-driven IRAs on Stitch Fix enable highly personalized recommendations that help consumer make choices beyond ordinary search and selection and offer the possibility of personal assistance in the decision-making process. (p.1000).....In the Stitch Fix context, customers with gain goals may positively value IRAs that help customers to make a price-quality decision regarding fashion products. (p.1004).....AI-driven IRAs likely enhance the quality of consumers’ decisions by using different underlying algorithms to make recommendations”. (Kim, Kang, & Bae, 2022, p. 1008)	AI Recommendation Influence on Decision Quality	AI recommendations’ effect on consumers’ decisions	Information Search and AI Recommendation
4.	“RS act as information filtering agents to simplify the decision making process for consumers or users of the system. The main objective of RS is to identify an item or a set of items from a plethora of available choices which may interest a user”. (Kumar and Bala, 2016, p.662)	AI Recommendation Influence on Decision Quality	AI recommendations’ effect on consumers’ decisions	Information Search and AI Recommendation

5.	“We propose that utilitarian versus hedonic decision-making domains modulate the influence of post hoc explanations on consumer responses to AI recommendations. (p.236)...the facilitating effect of post hoc explanations on consumers’ trust in AI recommendations is stronger in the utilitarian decision domains relative to the hedonic decision domains”. (Chen et al., 2023, p.247)	AI Recommendation Influence on Decision Quality	AI recommendations’ effect on consumers’ decisions	Information Search and AI Recommendation
6.	“Consumers’ preferences and willingness to pay (WTP) of products can be influenced by values displayed in personalized recommendations, and suggest that consumers’ behaviors are vulnerable toward recommendation agents (p.1)...The effect of recommendation type on consumer’s WTP of the focal product highly depends on which decision stage the consumer is in (p.12)... the positive effect of decision stage is significant and stronger when recommendations are complements”. (Zhang & Bockstedt, 2020, p. 12)	AI Recommendation Influence on Decision Quality	AI recommendations’ effect on consumers’ decisions	Information Search and AI Recommendation
7.	“When ChatGPT provided reduced recommendations... it had a significantly negative impact on the behavioral responses (i.e., visit intention) of decision makers...Our findings confirmed that option reduction by ChatGPT had a negative impact on decision-maker’s emotional reactions and behaviors”. (Shin et al.2023, p.14)	Behavioral Reactions to AI in Decision Contexts	AI recommendations’ effect on consumers’ decisions	Information Search and AI Recommendation
8.	“The results confirmed that a consumer’s purchase decision is associated with lower perceived uncertainty than a decision assisted by a recommendation agent, even though the AI considers the consumer’s past behavior and purchase choices.” (Rohden & Espartel, 2024, p. 907)	Behavioral Reactions to AI in Decision Contexts	AI recommendations’ effect on consumers’ decisions	Information Search and AI Recommendation
9.	“Anchors can impact the decision-making process in three stages: (1) retrieval and selection of information, (2) integration of information, and (3) formation of a response (p.960)...The study integrates ideas from behavioral decision theory and recommender systems, both from practical and theoretical	Behavioral Reactions to AI in Decision Contexts	AI recommendations’ effect on consumers’ decisions	Information Search and AI Recommendation

	standpoints. Experimental results provide strong evidence that biased output from recommender systems can significantly influence consumers' preference ratings". (Adomavicius et al., 2013, p.973)			
10.	"This article aims to understand whether people will shift from traditional to Generative AI-based search engines. The research examines the factors influencing purchase decisions and the likelihood of individuals using ChatGPT instead of traditional search engines and other sources." (Gude, 2023, p. 1)	Behavioral Reactions to AI in Decision Contexts	AI recommendations' effect on consumers' decisions	Information Search and AI Recommendation
11.	"We found that participants generally preferred ChatGPT, especially when they needed a large number of options for their decision-making process...To the best of our knowledge, this was the first empirical investigation of the impact of ChatGPT on consumer decision-making...our empirical results suggest that recommending a larger number of options, such as 60 or 70, can generate positive consumer responses". (Kim et al., 2023, p. 9).	Behavioral Reactions to AI in Decision Contexts	AI recommendations' effect on consumers' decisions	Information Search and AI Recommendation
12.	"The sense of autonomy improves the quality of AI-advised decisions, and by offering a feasible design strategy that leverages personal smartphones to address the uniqueness neglect of AI recommendation systems." (Hou et al., 2025, p.1)	Behavioral Reactions to AI in Decision Contexts	AI recommendations' effect on consumers' decisions	Information Search and AI Recommendation
13.	"Real-time adaptive personalization... infers the current preferences of consumers and generates content congruent with their preferences....Late-adaptive recommendations will have a higher level of match with the consumer's current preferences than early-adaptive recommendations...The ability to update customers' preference profiles is particularly relevant to hedonic products, which are often trendy and consumer tastes change from time to time." (Ho, Bodoff, & Tam, 2011, p. 665)	User Preference on Recommendation Type	Consumers' Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
14.	"In a group consumption context, group recommenders should lead to better choices than the widespread single recommender systems...They should also outperform conditions in which no	User Preference on Recommendation Type	Consumers' Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation

	automated recommender is present.(p.90)...The number of participants who followed recommendations was higher in the group recommender condition than in the single recommender condition. Specifically, 23% of the participants chose the top recommendation the group recommender offered, compared with 12% in the single recommender condition”.(Hennig-Thurau et al., 2012, p. 102).			
15.	“That is, the more participants cared about utilitarian attributes (values lower than 2.35 on the seven-point scale), the more they preferred an AI assistant over a human one. Conversely, the more participants cared about hedonic attributes (values higher than 3.36 on the seven-point scale), the more they preferred a human assistant over an AI one. (p. 74)...We found significant effects of goal and matching... In the case of an activated utilitarian goal, a greater proportion of participants chose the AI Realtor (76.8%) over the human Realtor (23.2%)...However, making unique preference matching salient turned preference for the AI Realtor into resistance despite the activated utilitarian goal...”.(Longoni & Cian, 2022, p. 77)	User Preference on Recommendation Type	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
16.	“We demonstrate that graphical rating display designs of recommender systems are more advantageous than numerical designs in reducing the biases, although none are able to remove biases completely”.(Adomavicius et. al. 2019, p.1)	User Preference on Recommendation Type	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
17.	“The present research empirically examines the interactive effects of recommendation source (AI vs. human) and attribute framing (vice vs. virtue) on consumer responses... consumers respond more negatively to AI (vs. human) recommending vice (vs. virtue) frame products...Study 3 showed that the humanized AI and AI-human hybrid improved the acceptance intention of the vice (vs. virtue) frame product recommendations...humanized (vs. non-humanized) AI improved acceptance intention via an increase in both perceived	User Preference on Recommendation Type	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation

	warmth and competence, whereas the AI-human hybrid (vs. AI) improved acceptance intention only via an increase in perceived competence”.(Yang et al., 2024, p. 11)			
18.	“The latent mean value of BingChat’s IC was higher than that of Amazon. (p.6)...indicating that recommendations by ChatGPT are more likely to be selected by consumers than those by the existing recommender system. (p.9)...ChatGPT has a greater impact on trust in the recommender system than the existing recommender system...This is thought to be because ChatGPT, unlike the existing recommender system, will value the interests of users more”. (Chang & Park, 2024, p. 9)	User Preference on Recommendation Type	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
19.	“Consumers who considered themselves ‘beer experts’ rated beers that were recommended by the user-based collaborative filtering system higher than those recommended by the content-based system...When the consumer expertise was high...consumers were more likely to recommend the BeerXpert to others when the system used user-based collaborative filtering recommendations”. (Chinchanachokchai et al., p. 7).	User Preference on Recommendation Type	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
20.	“For the previously stated reasons, we recommend that platforms adopt hybrid recommendation algorithms that assign different weights to different algorithms for individual users on the basis of user characteristics”. (Liu and Cong, p.788)	User Preference on Recommendation Type	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
21.	“We propose a novel two-sided recommender system framework, which considers emergence on both sides of the platform and adapts to the changing environment to influence agents. An agent-based simulation model is developed based on popular internet-based educational platforms to study this complex system and test our hypotheses. Our results show the value of a two-sided recommender system to tame complex search matching in platforms”. (Malgonde et al. 2020, p.49)	User Preference on Recommendation Type	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation

22.	“User recommendations are more effective than system recommendations in driving product sales.(p. 2)...The standardized coefficients and dominance weights of user recommendation volume and valence... are much larger than that of system recommendation strength... implying the stronger impact of user recommendations”. (Lin, 2014, p. 25).	User Preference on Recommendation Type	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
23.	“Participants reported a more favorable product attitude if the recommendation was provided by a human recommender rather than an AI recommender.(p.18)..The human (vs. AI) nature of the recommender increased participants’ purchase intention via an increase in both participants’ propensity to mentalize and tendency to regard the recommended product as self-relevant”. (Wien & Peluso, 2021, p. 21).	User Preference on Recommendation Type	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
24.	“The current research documents people's increased propensity to rely on AI-based recommendations over those proposed by human counterparts in the aftermath of marketplace discrimination. Such an increased preference happens because it serves as a coping strategy for consumers who have faced discrimination in the marketplace from other human actors.” (Talebi et al., 2025, p.1)	User Preference on Recommendation Type	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
25.	“The use of an RA was positively related to product search effectiveness... indicating that the use of an RA can increase the e-commerce website’s search ability.(p.340)...Our results indicated that the use of the RA enhances online consumers’ satisfaction with the website, provides a vehicle for better product promotion, a more effective product search process”. (Hostler et al., 2011, p. 342)	Role of Recommendation Agent in Information Search	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
26.	“Participants showed more favorable responses toward the company when the AI-generated information was presented in a precise (vs. imprecise) format. (p.1146)...Consumers’ attitude toward the products associated with AI and behavioral intention (i.e., recommendation to others) were more favorable when the	Role of Recommendation Agent in Information Search	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation

	information was given in a precise rather than an imprecise format”. (Kim et al., 2021, p. 1147)			
27.	“The experimental treatments were personalization (low versus high) and information-use transparency (low versus high). The distinct levels of personalization in this experiment were determined by the extent to which the service is able to find relevant events, provide recommendations, and tailor its newsletter to consumers’ actual preferences and online behavior. In the low personalization condition, users were able to search events according to their tastes or browse one of the proposed event categories. However, the high personalization treatment not only facilitated personalized search but also offered accurately tailored event recommendations, an individualized newsletter, and the option to integrate events into a user’s personal calendar”. (Karwatzki et al. 2017, p.382)	Role of Recommendation Agent in Information Search	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
28.	“Our experiment results reveal that the recommendation set size has a non-monotonic effect on consumers’ purchase probability... as much as 64% of the decrease in purchase probability (i.e., the choice overload effect) can be attributed to a decrease in consumers’ likelihood of starting a search (i.e., clicking on any recommended product)”. (Long et al., 2024, p.4)	Role of Recommendation Agent in Information Search	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
29.	“Our findings highlight the potential of query recommenders for increasing demand while enhancing consumer exploration and consumption diversity, particularly when deployed in tandem with auto-complete. Our study contributes to the literature on search behavior and recommendation systems, offering actionable insights for platform managers into the strategic design and integration of query recommenders to improve user engagement and market outcomes”. (Zheng et al. 2025, p.516)	Role of Recommendation Agent in Information Search	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
30.	“We find an inverted U-shaped relationship between the number of information cues and sales, with single cues yielding the highest sales compared to both more (dual cues) and less	Role of Recommendation Agent in Information Search	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation

	information (no cues). This nonlinear effect stems from the interplay between search intensity and efficiency. The no-cue condition increases search intensity but forces consumers to rely on a less efficient non-recommender search process. In contrast, the highly efficient dual-cue condition provides sufficient information for evaluation but discourages further exploration beyond recommenders. Single cues strike a balance, offering just enough information to aid product evaluation while maintaining high search intensity across both recommender and non-recommender tools”. (Fang et al., 2025, p.1)			
31.	“Consumers get a lot of AI recommendation information in line with their preferences. But in fact, this homogeneous information will greatly occupy the cognitive resources of consumers, making them have no energy to obtain other non-homogeneous information”. (Chen et al., 2022, p. 214)	Role of Recommendation Agent in Information Search	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
32.	“We theorized that in a perceived loss anomaly, individuals would be more likely to invest in acquiring new information via an explanation to understand why the anomalous recommendation was given in the first place (to update their posterior). Because seeking an explanation comes at a cost, an explanation would only be sought if the new information had sufficient value, for example, an opportunity to increase their expected utility versus the perceived loss.” (Jenkin et al. 2024, p. 664)	Role of Recommendation Agent in Information Search	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
33.	“Advances in information technology and e-commerce enable firms to make personalized offers to individual consumers based on information about the consumers. However, the collection and use of private information have caused serious concerns about privacy invasion by consumers, creating a personalization—privacy tradeoff.” (Lee et al. 2011, p.423)	Role of Recommendation Agent in Information Search	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation

34.	“Product recommendation systems are personalized sales assistance tools designed to make the product search process easier for consumers. (p.752)...We find that the level of bias depends on the firm’s level of knowledge about consumers’ product preferences and search costs”. (Choudhary & Zhang, 2023, p. 754)	Role of Recommendation Agent in Information Search	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
35.	“As the marketplace more accurately predicts consumers’ preferences, the equilibrium price first decreases and then increases, and both the marketplace’s and the sellers’ profits may decrease despite the improved recommendation accuracy. Moreover, recommending the most profitable product for each recommendation may reduce profits of the marketplace and the sellers, and the marketplace can benefit from excluding pricing information in its recommendation decisions to prevent sellers’ recommendation competition”. (Zhou & Zou, 2022, p.360).	Role of Recommendation Agent in Information Search	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
36.	“A higher perceived overload led to more RA consultation.(p,57)... perceived overload, rather than delivered information load, was the determining factor in predicting a participant’s conformance to a product recommendation”. (Aljukhadar et al., 2012, p.58)	Role of Recommendation Agent in Information Search	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
37.	“Consumers’ GenAI adoption may vary upon search purpose (search type), individual differences (travel motive) and situational differences (GenAI task-oriented customization level). (p.1725)...In decision-based information search, a high customization level for travel-related tasks is more likely to increase customers’ choice to adopt GenAI like ChatGPT”. (Luo et al., 2025, p.1732)	Role of Recommendation Agent in Information Search	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
38.	“It demonstrates that recommendation lists generated by SECT can cover more different travel products... compared with collaborative filtering methods, which are limited by sparse user-item matrices. (p.12)...We propose a novel recommendation engine (SECT) for travel products based on topic sequential	Role of Recommendation Agent in Information Search	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation

	patterns... to capture the preferences of tourists from their real-time click-streams and then recommend travel products for them”. (Zhu et al., 2017, p.15)			
39.	“When customers receive more product recommendations in a category, they search more in that category with generic query words, which indicates complementarity between recommendation and search. (p.84)...Compared with the control group, the customers in the treatment group reduce their recommendation browsing because the product recommendations become less relevant, and their searches are increased significantly”. (Yuan et al., 2025, p.85)	Role of Recommendation Agent in Information Search	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
40.	“Recommendations cause consumers to search in ‘choice mode’...induce a shift in consumers’ decision orientation in search from being directed at whether additional alternatives should be inspected to identifying the best alternative among those already encountered...Compared with unassisted search, recommendations lead consumers to assess a product they encounter in their search by comparing it less with the best one discovered up to that point and more with other previously inspected alternatives”. (Dellaert & Häubl, 2012, p. 277)	Role of Recommendation Agent in Information Search	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
41.	“Consumers often rely on their social connections or social technologies, such as (automated) system-generated recommender systems, to navigate the proliferation of diverse products and services offered in online and offline markets and cope with the corresponding choice overload”. (Adamopoulos, & Todri, 2024, p.1)	Role of Recommendation Agent in Information Search	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
42.	“If recommender systems lower consumers’ search costs and help them find better product matches... they are a highly appealing marketing technology . (p.240)...our results show that producers cannot passively rely on search tools like recommenders. Instead, such producers will need to continue exerting effort to ensure product discovery. (p.241)...Consumers,	Role of Recommendation Agent in Information Search	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation

	as a whole, are viewing and exploring fewer subcategories under the recommenders”. (Lee & Hosanagar, 2019, p.251).			
43.	“We find that the treated visitors browse products of higher net value...Moreover, additional RP page views under recommendations reduce the minimum, average, and median values... of the price distribution of searched products. (p.2)...We find evidence that visitors substitute other search tools with product recommendations, plausibly because recommendations help them search for higher-net-value products than other alternatives”. (Wan et al., 2023, p.3)	Role of Recommendation Agent in Information Search	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
44.	“The sales diversity-reducing (rich-get-richer) effect of recommendations is more pronounced when shopping for the search goods, whereas the search scope-broadening (long-tail) effect of recommendations is more pronounced for the experience goods. (p.1)...Recommendations increase search scope, both at the individual- and aggregate-level. In addition, this search scope-broadening effect of recommendation is more pronounced when shopping for experience goods than for search goods”. (Yi et al., 2022, p.7).	Role of Recommendation Agent in Information Search	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
45.	“Compared to search products, consumers count more on online word-of-mouth and advertising in forming an understanding of the experience product. They spend more time searching for experience product information online. (p.1906)...Our findings indicate that consumers show aversion to AI when recommending experience products but are receptive to AI recommending search products”. (Xie et al., 2022, p.1912)	Role of Recommendation Agent in Information Search	Consumers’ Search Preferences Toward Recommendation Agents	Information Search and AI Recommendation
46.	“An information search through a smart speaker can be refined by asking additional questions to the personal assistant. (p.6)...Young adults want to hear marketing messages on smart speakers that are for products they have explicitly asked about. (p.12)...The personal assistant is developing context about the user... this will enable the personal assistant to tailor database	Consumer Engagement with Conversational Agents during Search	AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search	Information Search and AI Conversation

	knowledge to fit conversations and advertising”. (Smith, 2018, p.5)			
47.	“Consumers may engage with AI-powered search tools driven by the desire for efficiency, accuracy, and personalized recommendations. The AI’s ability to learn from consumer interactions and adapt its responses could further motivate and shape consumer search behaviors. (p.5)... Consumers who perceive themselves as capable are more likely to engage in search tasks... reinforcing the importance of enhancing user perception of their abilities in the design and marketing of AI-powered search tools.” (Pham et al., 2024, p. 13)	Consumer Engagement with Conversational Agents during Search	AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search	Information Search and AI Conversation
48.	“Perceived contingency was positively related to gratifications of information seeking, social interaction, and entertainment consumers obtained from their interaction with social media brand chatbots. (p.8)...Social media brand chatbots were able to fulfill consumers’ utilitarian, social, and hedonic needs in a reciprocal and personalized manner... our findings suggest that consumer engagement... was driven by the need for brand-related information and social interaction...Among the three types of consumer gratification examined in our model, results concerning information-seeking gratification... advance understandings of how the perception of contingency relates to the motivational experiences behind engagement”. (Lin & Wu, 2023, p.9)	Consumer Engagement with Conversational Agents during Search	AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search	Information Search and AI Conversation
49.	“Consumers reveal preferences for relatively concrete features of a product... as this is the information format that most online retailers tend to employ in their IDAs. (p.232)...To assist consumers in their online search process, more and more companies are implementing IDAs...IDAs help consumers with navigating through large numbers of different products by asking the consumers about their preferences and matching these to the products offered”. (Köhler et al., 2011, p.233)	Consumer Engagement with Conversational Agents during Search	AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search	Information Search and AI Conversation

50.	“Voice artificial intelligence can be used during information searches to provide the right information to the consumer based on user-to-device dialogue. (p.2). Consumers’ willingness to seek opinions from external sources is deemed a critical driver of their perception of SHD utility in shopping search tasks”. (Canziani & MacSween, 2021, p.3)	Consumer Engagement with Conversational Agents during Search	AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search	Information Search and AI Conversation
51.	“For consumers, chatbots that provide tailored content could assist in consumer decision making, reduce consumer search costs and cognitive overload”. (Shumanov & Johnson, p.5)	Consumer Engagement with Conversational Agents during Search	AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search	Information Search and AI Conversation
52.	“The results showed main effects of both personalization and the social role on building attitudes toward the product (p.1)... With the rapid growth of voice shopping, marketers are already preparing for voice search engine optimization...How the snippets of product information are delivered through conversational agents and which tone and words are used could affect attitudes toward the product and eventually purchase intentions”. (Rhee & Choi, 2020, p.10)	Consumer Engagement with Conversational Agents during Search	AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search	Information Search and AI Conversation
53.	“Voice assistants represent a more natural interaction between consumers and the brand than information-retrieval and text-based reading. (p.2227)...Managers can provide incentives (advanced search capabilities or providing a smart working environment) for their users when they share their privacy information”. (Acikgoz et al., 2023, p.2238)	Consumer Engagement with Conversational Agents during Search	AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search	Information Search and AI Conversation
54.	“The search feature also provided a conversation topic between the owners, other family members and their visitors. For example, users engaged in collaborative search when engaged in trivia or other discussions”. (Ammari et al., 2019, p.17).	Consumer Engagement with Conversational Agents during Search	AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search	Information Search and AI Conversation
55.	“Voice assistants are increasingly replacing conventional search engines... consumers can use voice assistants to search for ‘the best smartwatch brand under \$50 (USD)’ or ask, ‘Which is the best organic honey on the market? (p.492)...This article	Consumer Engagement with Conversational Agents during Search	AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search	Information Search and AI Conversation

	represents an initial attempt to bridge this gap by proposing a consumption-value-based theoretical model and validating it with data from active users of voice assistants across three continents... the associations of perceived usefulness and perceived playfulness with consumers' use of voice assistants, i.e., information search and task function". (Malodia et al., 2024, p.503)			
56.	"Chatbots are required to not only provide customers with necessary consultancy and guidance but also communicate friendly and socially. (p.1)...Our findings show that suggestive guidance has a stronger effect than informative guidance... and searching task showed a stronger influence than browsing task. (p.18)...The match between information format and task significantly led to the cognitive fit...this fit in cognition improved the decision-making performance, not only enhanced the quality of decision but also reduced the effort of the customers". (Chen, Le, & Tran, 2021, p.19)	Consumer Engagement with Conversational Agents during Search	AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search	Information Search and AI Conversation
57.	"AI streaming assistant increases sales by 3.00% and reduces the product return rates by 12.55%. Our exploration of plausible mechanisms suggests that access to an AI streaming assistant increases consumers' perception of intelligent information provision (and, in parallel, interruption), which in turn reduces (and increases) uncertainty in decision making." (Wang et al., 2025, p.1)	Consumer Engagement with Conversational Agents during Search	AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search	Information Search and AI Conversation
58.	"These findings suggest that when the AI chatbot provides high-quality information and is perceived as useful and cool, users are more satisfied and likely to remain loyal.(p.7)...This study brings coolness theory to the forefront of research on chatbots by demonstrating that the quality of the information delivered by chatbots can be perceived as cool by users when the information is quick, relevant, reliable, and concise." (Niu & Mvondo, 2024, p. 9)	Consumer Engagement with Conversational Agents during Search	AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search	Information Search and AI Conversation

59.	<p>“On the other hand, non-transactional activity involves activities that require more thought. Often, consumers who are involved in non-transactional activity are in the initial stages of the buyer’s journey. These may include awareness and/or consideration...When consumers are not able to get an adequate answer from a voice assistant, they would turn to an online search. (p.10)...The research was conducted based on general information search and purchasing information search. This empirical model should also be tested on specific product searches or specific information searches”. (Moriuchi, 2019, p.10)</p>	<p>Search Interaction Shaped by Conversational Agents</p>	<p>AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search</p>	<p>Information Search and AI Conversation</p>
60.	<p>“VAFs that include informational capabilities (e.g., news briefings, information search) are more positively received by investors since such capabilities allow users to self-extend parts of their identity and, in turn, self-expand as they absorb and trust the content provided to them. (p.1220)...Consumers can efficiently access the information that they need by asking questions aloud and engaging in a realistic conversation with voice assistants. (p.1223)...Investors reward firms that release VAFs that provide easy access to information”. (Bahmani et al., 2022, p.1228)</p>	<p>Search Interaction Shaped by Conversational Agents</p>	<p>AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search</p>	<p>Information Search and AI Conversation</p>
61.	<p>“We contrast the patterns found in information-seeking dialogues that are being used for research purposes with the patterns found in virtual reference interviews that were conducted by professional librarians. The insights we provide (1) establish close relations between conversational search and other conversational AI tasks and (2) uncover limitations of existing conversational datasets to inform future data collection tasks”. (Vakulenko et al., 2021, p.1)</p>	<p>Search Interaction Shaped by Conversational Agents</p>	<p>AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search</p>	<p>Information Search and AI Conversation</p>
62.	<p>“We analyze large-scale archival data of consumer-level purchase records from Alibaba, the world’s largest e-commerce platform, to empirically investigate how consumers’ adoption of</p>	<p>Search Interaction Shaped by Conversational Agents</p>	<p>AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search</p>	<p>Information Search and AI Conversation</p>

	Tmall Genie affects their consumption. The results show that the average consumer's weekly spending on the e-commerce platform increased by 16.6% within the first four months after adopting voice AI." (Sun et al., 2025, p.1)			
63.	"Since search products primarily involve utilitarian and information-driven buying decisions, the information about them is readily accessible. (p.5)...Chatbots often excel when users seek specific information, offering a more efficient mode for cognitive tasks during transactions. (p.4)...Customers engaging with text-based chatbots for search products display more favorable engagement in online shopping scenarios". (Rohit et al., 2024, p.7).	Search Interaction Shaped by Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search	Information Search and AI Conversation
64.	"Consumers may focus more on whether one subject can effectively provide the information they need and help them make a purchasing decision during the product consultation...For search products, participants whose needs were in a state of higher certainty... felt AI chatbots to be more effective... thus leading to a higher willingness to choose them. (p.648)...We confirm the perceived effectiveness of AI chatbots from the perspective of information consultation and certainty reinforcement". (Zhu et al., p.649)	Search Interaction Shaped by Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search	Information Search and AI Conversation
65.	"Shopbots are thought to be a significant driver of lower search costs. Internet shopbots are automated tools that allow customers to search for prices and product characteristics from online retailers at a click of a button. (p.446)...Shopbots may be able to maximize their revenue by intelligently designing their interfaces to improve consumer search without eliminating retailer differentiation". (Smith, 2002, p.452)	Search Interaction Shaped by Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search	Information Search and AI Conversation
66.	"AI chatbots are likely to be more effective at providing complete, current and detailed objective product information based on mechanical or analytical system learning. (p.4)... When the product attribute emphasized was framed as a functional	Search Interaction Shaped by Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search	Information Search and AI Conversation

	attribute, there was no difference in perceived information quality between the scenarios...However, when the product attribute... was experiential, perceived information quality was higher when participants' consultations were responded to by HFLEs". (Ruan & Mezei, 2022, p.7)			
67.	"A key purpose of a VA is to relay information to users based on their requests. Information that is current, relevant, accurate, clear, and reliable is considered to be of high quality...VAs will seek the most relevant and reliable information to return to users... drawing on specific applications (e.g., Alexa Skills) and the highest-ranked search results from search engines". (McLean et al., 2021, p.315)	Search Interaction Shaped by Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Consumer Engagement in Search	Information Search and AI Conversation
68.	"We found that perceived power over AI assistants can mitigate users' risk perceptions regarding voice shopping...The fit between perceived power over AI and individual desire for power can decrease users' perceived risk regarding shopping via AI, which is especially vital for the business monetization of AI technology in e-commerce". (Hu et al., 2022, p.9)	Task Facilitation through Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation
69.	"The results show that smart experiences influence consumers' passion for technology, while passion explains their intimacy and commitment...Consumer intimacy and commitment for SVAs lead to service loyalty". (Hernandez-Ortega & Ferreira, 2021, p.1).	Task Facilitation through Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation
70.	"Performance expectancy is also an important antecedent of continuance intention to use. That is, the utilitarian and functional benefits that users perceive they derive from using VAs to perform their daily tasks is a very important reason they continue using them. (p.2285)...Perceived performance expectancy positively influenced continuance intention to use". (Molinillo et al., 2023, p.2281)	Task Facilitation through Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation
71.	Subjects in our study evaluated chatbots in a fashion similar to interpersonal interactions... Future-oriented subjects are	Task Facilitation through Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation

	conducive to a favourable relationship with competent chatbots as competency-related traits are instrumental to task accomplishment...Chatbots, although designed to help consumers with queries and facilitate sales, can, therefore, also act as a promotional tool for the brand and the company. (Roy & Naidoo, 2021, p.31)			
72.	“Voice assistants give advice based on consumers’ preferences and habits...This feature...guides consumers during their purchase decision-making processes by providing product/service recommendations. (p.329)...Consumers receive personalized recommendations which provide appropriate information, increasing the effectiveness of the recommendations which, consequently, facilitate their purchase decision-making processes”. (Flavián et al., 2023, p.331)	Task Facilitation through Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation
73.	“The interaction modality speech has a significant positive effect on efficiency. (p.848)...The positive effects of interacting via speech on users’ perceived efficiency and cognitive effort also support our assumption that speech recognition technology has improved in recent years, enabling users to realize the benefits of natural speech – it being faster and requiring less cognitive effort than text-based interactions”. (Rzepka et al., 2022, p.849).	Task Facilitation through Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation
74.	“The voice shopping experience with the Alexa app aids caregivers in catering to the needs of elderly individuals by providing convenient shopping, voice-activated control, reminders, smart home integration, and access to information”. (Kumar et al., 2024, p.1).	Task Facilitation through Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation
75.	“The results show that, over 12 months, the quality of interactivity, reliability, personalization, and satisfaction with the IVAs experience are the key drivers of consumers’ continuous use of IVAs while such influence is dependent on the purpose of use”. (Otoo et al., 2025, p.2521)	Task Facilitation through Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation

76.	“Individuals can use digital assistants to perform basic personal task management functions as well as for more advanced capabilities and connected-device integrations. (p.9)...This technology can serve as a critical technology enabler in the continued growth and evolution of conversational commerce”. (Brill et al., 2019, p.24)	Task Facilitation through Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation
77.	“A wider VA task range and greater VA accuracy signal greater VA intelligence. VA intelligence maps onto VA competence... today the tasks VAs execute are simple enough”. (Guha et al., 2023, p.860)	Task Facilitation through Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation
78.	“The proposed MarkBot...can further alleviate this success rate for the business houses, with dynamic yet personalized interactions, to enhance customer service aspects...This study tries to establish the chatbots as service agents rather than mere conventional support agents to browse various issues or catalogs”. (Kushwaha & Kar, 2021, p.13)	Task Facilitation through Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation
79.	“The results mostly support the validity of the proposed research model, which asserts that VPA device adoption is determined by perception of the utilitarian and hedonic values, and that these are composed of perceived usefulness, perceived enjoyment, portability, automation, content quality, and visual attractiveness”. (Yang & Lee, 2018, p.81)	Task Facilitation through Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation
80.	“Process explanations based on users’ profiles and their purchase behavior show the strongest effects in improving fairness perceptions (p.1)...User-based process explanations demonstrated a significant effect on systemic fairness... as they consider users’ profiles and behaviors the most”. (Weith & Matt, 2023, p.14)	Task Facilitation through Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation
81.	“Personalized offerings provide users with reduced cognitive overload and convenience...Personalization of IVAs has been shown to enhance user satisfaction, system understandability, quality of presented information, and task efficiency, particularly	Task Facilitation through Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation

	in IVAs where the presented information is mostly a voice-only form”. (Alimamy & Kuhail, 2023, p.4).			
82.	“Study 1 found that, in general, consumers express more willingness to purchase low-involvement (vs. high-involvement) products when using a VA device. (p.1075)...Consumers using a VA evaluate search products...more positively than experiential products...VAs are often used to make habitual purchases”. (Tassiello et al., 2021, p.1075)	Task Facilitation through Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation
83.	“The tasks that VAs are being used for are more hedonic and functional in nature which, by their simplistic nature, do not demand levels of trust or assurance. (p.636)...I can ask which shops are open but for products you would need a specific idea in mind, and I am not even sure Home will understand anyway”. (Pitardi & Marriott, 2021, p.637)	Task Facilitation through Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation
84.	“Firms adopting such technologies will be able to achieve more personalized and efficient services, thereby contributing to value creation. (p.180)...If service delivery mainly aims to fulfil utilitarian needs, users are expected to value speed and convenience (i.e., usefulness), since there is little need for social interaction. (p.187)...Findings reveal that DVA use is mainly driven by functional elements such as its usefulness, especially regarding more advanced users”. (Fernandes & Oliveira, p.190)	Task Facilitation through Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation
85.	“Low-competency older users experience significantly superior cognitive outcomes (i.e., lower information load) and functional outcomes (i.e., greater self-efficacy and ease of use) when the digital assistant focuses strictly on task-oriented interaction style. (p.323)...Older users’ Internet competency moderates the effect of digital assistant interaction style on the functional outcomes... with low-competency older users showing significantly higher functional outcomes when the digital assistant employs task-oriented (vs. social) dialog”. (Chattaraman et al., 2019, p.326)	Task Facilitation through Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation

86.	“Thus, users turn to voice controlled technology due to their usefulness and convenience to aid them in the completion of tasks, accordingly influencing the continuous use of the technology (p.34)...The findings of this study reveal that in-home voice assistants are used for utilitarian purposes. Thus, individuals are motivated to use in-home voice assistants to help them complete tasks, look up information, seek support and process orders”. (McLean & Osei-Frimpong, 2019, p.35)	Perceived Efficiency in Task Support by Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation
87.	“From a task-fit perspective, SVA can complete routine tasks with ease reducing users’ cognitive load... we can say that SVA complete tasks efficiently and consistently. (p.9)...Many users use voice interaction features on their phones to search information or to get directions. Similarly, many users turn to SVA to perform a basic search, play a song, or read news”. (Mishra et al., 2022, p.10)	Perceived Efficiency in Task Support by Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation
88.	“SHAs’ recommendations may be easy to obtain as well as accurate and useful...Our findings strongly support the idea that SHA design should prioritize algorithm transparency... explaining how the SHA came to a particular decision or recommendation”. (Raff et al., 2024, p.12)	Perceived Efficiency in Task Support by Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation
89.	“The quantitative analysis demonstrates that task completion is characterized by a higher perception of the chatbot’s conversational ability and user satisfaction. The chatbot should propose correct recipe suggestions following a short dialogue, without the user needing to provide too much input...The chatbot should propose correct recipe suggestions following a short dialogue, without the user needing to provide too much input”. (Rese & Tränker, 2024, p.1)	Perceived Efficiency in Task Support by Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation
90.	“The findings suggest that the incongruence between speaking and listening can undermine the social presence voice assistants created for consumers, resulting in decreased consumer trust and undesirable consumer behaviors for voice marketing....Social	Perceived Efficiency in Task Support by Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation

	presence is an important consumer experience in voice marketing because it can prompt consumers to build a para-social relationship with voice assistants... [which leads to] acceptance of voice recommendations and purchases via voice assistants”. (Hu et al., 2023, p.123)			
91.	“A VA is considered helpful for shopping decisions provided it helps alleviate the consumers’ load by gathering, sorting, and evaluating a vast amount of product information in increasingly complex marketplaces. (p.7)...Our results show that an empathic (vs. standard) AI agent results in higher scores not only in the social-emotional AI agent attributes, but in all ten considered constructs. Thus, the positive consumer responses to AI empathy may produce a halo effect on all other characteristics of the VA”. (Mari et al., 2024, p.13)	Perceived Efficiency in Task Support by Conversational Agents	AI Conversational Agents and Task Efficiency	Information Search and AI Conversation
92.	“AI voice assistants possessing a heightened level of anthropomorphism can augment the sense of social presence and engage in interactions with consumers, providing companionship and addressing their social needs while alleviating loneliness...AI voice assistants exhibiting a heightened degree of anthropomorphism can deliver more comprehensive and valuable information, thereby enhancing the efficiency and quality of human–computer interaction”. (Zhou et al., 2023, p.13)	Preference for anthropomorphic agents in repeated search	Anthropomorphism in Consumer Engagement and Search	Information Search and AI Anthropomorphism
93.	“Anthropomorphised products can lead consumers to like them more... see the product as a friend and keep it for longer, as they perceive replacing it as being disloyal towards their friend. (p.696)...Informants in the ‘VCSA as a servant’ group... praised the VCSAs’ refreshing usefulness and cherished them as self-enhancing and empowering helpers who facilitated their information search”. (Schweitzer et al., 2019, p.703)	Preference for anthropomorphic agents in repeated search	Anthropomorphism in Consumer Engagement and Search	Information Search and AI Anthropomorphism

94.	<p>“Given the numerous daily interactions between users and various platforms, providing information about the benefits of using VAs... will be crucial for their development...The humanization of VAs is a crucial aspect in instilling the necessary confidence among users... incorporating a humanized voice enhances the overall user experience...The primary focus of the study centered on general information and purchase searches...”.(Calahorra-Candao & Martín-de Hoyos, 2024, p.9)</p>	<p>Preference for anthropomorphic agents in repeated search</p>	<p>Anthropomorphism in Consumer Engagement and Search</p>	<p>Information Search and AI Anthropomorphism</p>
95.	<p>“ANTH can create positive outcomes for engagement, which could be a greater feeling of connectedness toward a nonhuman agent... More engagement occurs when the nonhuman agent is able to interact with the consumer naturally. (p.5)...The interesting result in Study 1 was the serial mediators of ANTH and engagement. Based on the results, VAs may have the stigma of being a robot, and thus, the expectation of ANTH did not have much of an impact on intention to re-use the VAs. However, the results did suggest that in order for engagement to exist, ANTH of a bot is essential”. (Moriuchi, 2020, p.9)</p>	<p>Preference for anthropomorphic agents in repeated search</p>	<p>Anthropomorphism in Consumer Engagement and Search</p>	<p>Information Search and AI Anthropomorphism</p>
96.	<p>“Consumers’ exploratory behavior leads to consumer satisfaction and consumers’ willingness to continue using voice assistant (p.1)... VA manifesting functional intelligence, sincerity, and creativity traits can enhance consumers’ perceived control during voice interactions... especially when the VA offers effective, efficient, sincere, honest, and current information”. (Poushneh, 2021, p.7)</p>	<p>Preference for anthropomorphic agents in repeated search</p>	<p>Anthropomorphism in Consumer Engagement and Search</p>	<p>Information Search and AI Anthropomorphism</p>
97.	<p>“Consumers are likely to anthropomorphize voice assistants due to voice-based conversational interactions. Voice is known to be a powerful anthropomorphic cue. (p.2)...For a search product, consumers’ evaluation of the recommended product will be unaffected by the shopping medium type. (p.5)...In addition, the study indicates that consumers’ evaluation of search products was not affected by the shopping medium type. This suggests</p>	<p>Preference for anthropomorphic agents in repeated search</p>	<p>Anthropomorphism in Consumer Engagement and Search</p>	<p>Information Search and AI Anthropomorphism</p>

	that retailers using voice assistants should focus on search products initially while consumers continue to build relationships with their voice assistants”. (Whang & Im, 2020, p.12)			
98.	“The effect of anthropomorphic cues on perceived product personalization is more pronounced when consumers experience high (vs. low) situational loneliness. (p.12)...Anthropomorphic verbal cues facilitate consumers’ product evaluations through a human-like interaction with a chatbot. (p.13)...Consumers experiencing situational loneliness perceive products offered by chatbots as more personalized”. (Sidlauskiene et al., 2023, p.14)	Anthropomorphism boosts product impression	Anthropomorphism effect in Product Evaluation	Information Search and AI Anthropomorphism
99.	“Users interacting with an embodied PRA will be more likely to treat the interaction as an interpersonal conversation (p.141)...This study found strong evidence for the influence of humanoid embodiments and output modalities on enhancing social interactions between a PRA and its users. (p.164)...An agent will be more likely to be accepted and employed by online shoppers when it affords a compelling socially rich and enjoyable interaction experience, on top of its underlying functionalities of product search and comparisons”. (Qiu & Benbasat, 2009, p.167)	Anthropomorphism boosts product impression	Anthropomorphism effect in Product Evaluation	Information Search and AI Anthropomorphism
100.	“Anthropomorphic versions of consumer products have, for example, been shown to elicit greater moral care from consumers and greater trust in non-human technological products. (p.1015)...Consumers develop greater trust in anthropomorphized products by establishing an emotional relationship to non-human agents...Anthropomorphic versions of consumer products have, for example, been shown to elicit greater moral care from consumers and greater trust in non-human technological products such as polygraph tests and autonomous vehicles”. (Benlian et al., 2019, p.1016)	Anthropomorphism boosts product impression	Anthropomorphism effect in Product Evaluation	Information Search and AI Anthropomorphism

101.	The results show that, in support of our theorizing, the positive effect of turn-taking on recommendation acceptance was sequentially mediated by greater perceived interface humanness and increased brand intimacy (Bergner et al., 2023, p.752)	Anthropomorphism boosts product impression	Anthropomorphism effect in Product Evaluation	Information Search and AI Anthropomorphism
102.	“Information processing theory would predict that the fun, entertainment, and human touch resulting from the interaction can serve as peripheral cues for consumers to form their evaluations of the Web site, product, and consequently, their purchase intention. (p.62)...In this study, we demonstrated that when participants had only limited static product information, the availability of an AIA enhanced affective evaluation of the Web site, product evaluation, and purchase intention. (p.65)...Although the AIA may be effective in providing a human touch and enhancing affective evaluation of the Web site, if enhancing product attitude is the goal, providing detailed information on the Web site can result in the desired response”. (Sivaramakrishnan et al., 2007, p.66)	Anthropomorphism boosts product impression	Anthropomorphism effect in Product Evaluation	Information Search and AI Anthropomorphism
103.	“Users looked for a comparable amount of time at the results list and the additional information before making a decision... the improvements can be solely attributed to the use of the social-information overlays...The combination of the user profile overlay and the social-rating overlays was effective in reducing the need to consult external sources to select information”. (Orso et al., 2022, p.1283)	Semantic Modeling and Adaptive Search Interfaces	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval
104.	“The article reports on an exploratory study that assesses the results produced by emerging artificial intelligence (AI)- and large language model-driven search tools in response to a series of queries and prompts based on four scenarios of information-intensive tasks of university students and researchers”. (Chowdhury & Chowdhury, 2024, p.1)	Semantic Modeling and Adaptive Search Interfaces	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval

105.	“This study examines how different incentive structures—commission-based, best-only, and mixed incentives—affect search behavior and performance in human–AI collaborative decision-making during combinatorial search tasks”. (Seo et al., 2025, p.1)	Semantic Modeling and Adaptive Search Interfaces	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval
106.	“In the context of online search engines, HDLDA identifies not only topics in short search queries and web pages, but also how the topics in search queries relate to the topics in the corresponding top search results. (p.1)...HDLDA is specifically designed for contexts in which one type of document (in our context, search queries) is semantically related to another type of document (in our context, web pages)”. (Liu & Toubia, 2021, p.2)	Semantic Modeling and Adaptive Search Interfaces	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval
107.	“Our results suggest that the quality of the subsequent answers is impacted by the quality of the first displayed answer. We further show that the impact of the first displayed answer is larger when the answerers are more familiar with the forum but smaller when the forum provides tips for answering questions”. (Mousavi et al. 2020, P.1073)	Semantic Modeling and Adaptive Search Interfaces	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval
108.	“In our study, we propose an automatic way of examining keyword ambiguity based on probabilistic topic models from machine learning and computational linguistics. We examine the effect of keyword ambiguity on keyword performance using a hierarchical Bayesian approach that allows for topic-specific effects and nonlinear position effects, and jointly models click-through rate (CTR) and ad position (rank)”. (Gong et al. 2018, p.805)	Semantic Modeling and Adaptive Search Interfaces	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval
109.	“Under the ship-then-shop model, the firm leverages its AI capability to predict consumers’ preferences and ships the product to them. (p.1)...Unlike the traditional shopping model, which begins with consumer search, under the ship-then-shop	Semantic Modeling and Adaptive Search Interfaces	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval

	model the firm ships a product to the consumer who then decides whether to purchase it”. (Choi et al., 2022, p.28)			
110.	“By utilising adaptive composition and presentation techniques, PIR systems could potentially engage users into personalised search sessions and motivate them to subscribe to the notion of search as an interactive process”. (Steichen et al., 2012, p.39).	Semantic Modeling and Adaptive Search Interfaces	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval
111.	“Adaptive VIBE can improve the precision and the productivity of the personalized search system while helping users to discover more diverse sets of information”. (Ahn & Brusilovsky, 2013, p.1139)	Semantic Modeling and Adaptive Search Interfaces	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval
112.	“We propose a personalized ranking mechanism based on a user’s search and click history....Our machine-learning framework consists of three modules: (a) feature generation, (b) normalized discounted cumulative gain-based LambdaMART algorithm, and (c) feature selection wrapper. (p.1)...We present a general framework for search personalization that employs... the LambdaMART ranking algorithm... to maximize the predictive ability of the framework. (p.3)...The quality of personalized results increases monotonically with the length of a user’s search history... Our findings thus suggest that transactional and informational queries are more likely to benefit from personalization”. (Yoganarasimhan, 2019, p.4)	AI-Powered Personalization and Ranking in Search	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval
113.	“The proposed system analyses the clickstream data obtained from an ecommerce site and predicts the preference level of the customer for the products clicked but not purchased using efficient classifiers such as decision trees, artificial neural networks and extended trees. (p.1503)... Rough Set Leader clustering finds out all the leaders in the dataset in a single iteration... grouping like-minded users and finding preferences for the product saves enormous amount of time as the data set is very vast.” (Gupta & Dixit, 2018, p. 1506)	AI-Powered Personalization and Ranking in Search	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval

114.	“Coupling machine learning and NLG with a content editor, we propose a semiautomated approach for SEO content generation. Not only is the output similar to humangenerated content along a number of linguistic dimensions, but it outperforms manual content creation in search engine rankings, production efficiency, and engagement”. (Reisenbichler et al., 2022,p.450)	AI-Powered Personalization and Ranking in Search	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval
115.	“This engine analyzes data and generates association rules based on keywords that are used for searching and products that are added to shopping cart. So the aim of this study is to offer products, which users might be highly interested, and to get higher conversion rate. (p.452)... Products that are the most likely to be added to the shopping cart are displayed to the user... Display module selects five products according to confidence of the rule and shows them as a small picture with name and price”. (Cakir & Aras, 2012, p.454)	AI-Powered Personalization and Ranking in Search	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval
116.	“Our findings offer valuable insights into the operation and management of online health platforms. The experimental results demonstrate that when recommending HCSs to NPs, the proposed CNN-MAB method achieves average performance improvements of 22.8% in re- call, 17.1% in MRR, and 16.4% in coverage compared to baseline methods”. (Ni and Yang, 2025, p.2353)	AI-Powered Personalization and Ranking in Search	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval
117.	“Improves consumer efficiency by reducing search effort and increasing downloads; (ii) random sorting combined with product popularity disclosure stimulates more search activity, potentially boosting advertising revenue; and (iii) sorting based on personalized ranking with displayed product popularity enhances engagement by increasing both downloads and search efficiency”. (Osgouei et al., 2025, p.1)	AI-Powered Personalization and Ranking in Search	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval
118.	“We find that the impact of consuming personalized content (vs. other types of content or no content) on discussion intent varies depending on the strength of an individual’s identification with	AI-Powered Personalization and Ranking in Search	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval

	the domain. For weak identifiers, personalized content increases discussion intent, whereas for strong identifiers, it decreases intent. Process evidence highlights two underlying psychological forces: enhanced enjoyment of the domain and diminished confidence in domain knowledge. Personalized content increases discussion intent for weak identifiers—users whose intent is likely driven by high enjoyment”. (Lee & Johar, 2025, p.1)			
119.	We find that a more precise search algorithm improves consumers’ click-through and purchase rates drastically and instantaneously, but it comes at the cost of a significant decrease in consumer engagement and unplanned purchases over a longer time horizon. On average, consumers who used to spend more time searching now conduct 5.5% fewer searches, spend 4.1% less time on the platform, and decrease their spending on related categories by 2.2% in the week after the search precision increases. (Zhou et al., 2024, p. 1)	AI-Powered Personalization and Ranking in Search	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval
120.	“Our method is able to address the cold-start problem for new links... This feature of our model is particularly important for search engines and advertisers because it is critical for them to improve predictions for new links quickly (p.6380)...Our model can generate meaningful substantive output that may lead to important insights for search engines and advertisers... It can also automatically identify, interpret, and quantify whether and how user content preferences vary across contexts”. (Liu et al., 2021, p.6392)	AI-Powered Personalization and Ranking in Search	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval
121.	“We study competition between two firms that personalize product offerings to consumers. Firms have private, imperfect signals of each consumer’s ideal location and offer each consumer a different product without observing the competitor’s product offering”. (Du and Ning, 2025, p.1)	AI-Powered Personalization and Ranking in Search	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval

122.	“This outcome provides evidence that consumers express satisfaction with the sole AI-CE implementation by retailers (e.g., Amazon’s Alexa and Alibaba’s Wenwen). The reason is that consumers experiencing misfit will ascertain the product’s fitness through AI-CE, consequently yielding a high surplus”. (Cheng et al. 2025, p.727)	AI-Powered Personalization and Ranking in Search	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval
123.	“We proposed a novel session-based recommendation system that incorporates RNN models into representing long-term tracking sessions. The proposed deep learning model based on the bidirectional LSTM technique with the self-attention technique mimics users’ two-stage decision process”. (Cheng & Chen, 2022, p.9)	AI-Powered Personalization and Ranking in Search	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval
124.	“We develop a theoretical model where the recommendation policy selects products based on consumers’ preference rankings, learned from personal data. Unlike conventional recommendation policies that primarily focus on prospering from meeting consumer satisfaction, our approach applies differential privacy to mitigate the risk of exposing personal information to man-in-the-middle attackers during the transmission of recommendations over communication networks, such as the Internet”.(Fu et al., 2025, p.1)	AI-Powered Personalization and Ranking in Search	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval
125.	“We therefore develop a novel stochastic variational Bayesian framework to achieve fast, scalable, and accurate estimation in such big-data settings and apply it to a MovieLens data set of movie ratings and semantic tags. We show that our model yields interesting insights about movie preferences and makes much better predictions than a benchmark model that uses only product covariates”.(Ansari et al., 2018, p.987)	AI-Powered Personalization and Ranking in Search	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval
126.	“PDM is capable of predicting the incremental benefits for a consumer in the search process..(p.11)...We found that PDM performs better than the other methods with the well-known 18	AI-Powered Personalization and Ranking in Search	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval

	effective rating prediction techniques. Further experiments showed that PDM is robust with regard to various parameters and performs especially well in contexts in which user heterogeneity levels are high”. (Wang et al., 2015, p.25).			
127.	“This paper proposes Multi-Modal Self-Supervised Learning Algorithm Based Product Recommendation (MMSLRec). 1) Data augmentation by self-supervised adversarial perturbation generation learning is performed to supplement the missing interaction information of tailed products to solve the common data sparsity problem in product recommendation. 2) A multimodal representation learning module is introduced to capture deep features in image and text modalities using AlexNet and Bert, respectively, in order to avoid the recommendation accuracy degradation problem caused by insufficient data feature learning. 3) Learning the user’s perceived strength in different modalities, using the user co-occurrence matrix to fuse the features and make recommendations.” (Gao et al., 2025, p.15371)	AI-Powered Personalization and Ranking in Search	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval
128.	“The results uncover that DL models are capable of extracting information from longitudinal features for overall higher and statistically significant performance”. (Díaz et al., 2025, p.609)	AI-Powered Personalization and Ranking in Search	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval
129.	“Most recommender systems utilise two approaches of information filtering: collaborative filtering (CF)... and content-based (CB). (p.1)...Aided by continually evolving machine learning technology, recommender systems (RSs) have become a mainstay in Web 3.0”. (Oh et al., 2021, p.2).	AI-Powered Personalization and Ranking in Search	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval
130.	“We present the multi-choice market discovery algorithm to estimate the MC-RLM, extending single-purchase methods to multi-purchase settings. We also introduce behavior-reveal-preference (BRP) rules, using customer behavior data (e.g., clicks, cart additions) to enhance preference estimation.” (Lin et al. 2025, p.1).	AI-Powered Personalization and Ranking in Search	AI techniques for information search and retrieval tasks	Information Search and AI Retrieval

131.	“Typed search modality (vs. voice search modality) led to higher purchase intentions and behavior... consumers performing a typed search are more likely to be in an action-oriented mindset, whereas consumers performing a voice search are more likely to be in a deliberative mindset. (p.1236)...Typed searching activates a relatively action-oriented mindset, whereas voice searching activates a relatively deliberative mindset”. (King et al., 2022, p.1239)	AI modality influences search experience	AI modalities in information search	Information Search and AI Retrieval
132.	“Our findings reveal that high-arousal language significantly increases interaction willingness, with social identity mediating this relationship. Most notably, we discovered a “psychological defense-curiosity paradox”: shadow visual atmospheres, despite triggering initial defensive reactions, enhance engagement more effectively than light atmospheres, challenging conventional “brighter is better” design assumptions.” (Bai et al., 2025, p.3921	AI modality influences search experience	AI modalities in information search	Information Search and AI Retrieval
133.	Voice interface enables quick and efficient product discovery, making it highly informative. The engaging and enjoyable voice interface adds an interesting dimension to product searches. (p.304)... Increased satisfaction increases consumer engagement with the e-commerce website and motivates consumers to adopt and continue to use voice modality over text for purchasing products online. (Gupta & Mukherjee, 2025, p.306).	AI modality influences search experience	AI modalities in information search	Information Search and AI Retrieval
134.	“Search engines constantly aim to improve user experience by providing search results in different formats, such as text-only, image, and video... this warranted a systematic investigation of the effects of the types and formats of search results on BI”. (Diwanji et al., 2023 p.5)	AI modality influences search experience	AI modalities in information search	Information Search and AI Retrieval
135.	“Compared to traditional typing and searching methods, the “voice” presentation by VAs greatly increases consumer trust and perceived usefulness in the setting of low-involvement	AI modality influences search experience	AI modalities in information search	Information Search and AI Retrieval

	products. On the other hand, the “voice and visual” presentation format is the favoured option for high-involvement items.” (Hari, Sharma, & Verma, 2025, p.475)			
136.	“Our findings indicate that the forecasting model with the selected search keywords outperformed the benchmark ARMAX model without feature selection in forecasting tourism demand and hotel occupancy. Therefore, machine learning methods can identify the most useful search query data to significantly improve forecasting accuracy in tourism and hospitality”. (Li et. 2020, p. 1214)	AI modality influences search experience	AI modalities in information search	Information Search and AI Retrieval
137.	“Vocalizing (vs. typing) a query leads consumers to provide more specific, detailed descriptions of what they are seeking, which in turn yield search results that they are more satisfied with. (p.533)...When speaking to voice technology, we might experience a sense of audience, and a desire to be understood by that audience... consumers give more forethought to how they want to phrase their query before saying it out loud”. (vs. typing it). (Melumad, 2023, p.535)	AI modality influences search experience	AI modalities in information search	Information Search and AI Retrieval
138.	“Our results reveal that matching communication modality with product type (i.e., speaking about hedonic products; writing about utilitarian products) shapes consumers’ choices and increases their choice satisfaction. Specifically, speaking fosters a feeling-based verbalizing focus, while writing triggers a reason-based focus”. (Schindler et al., 2023, p.646).	AI modality influences search experience	AI modalities in information search	Information Search and AI Retrieval
139.	“A text-based assistant is perceived as more human-like compared to a voice-based assistant... which in turn positively influences brand attitudes and purchase intention. (p.402)...Voice as a communication modality can increase persuasion knowledge by being cognitively more demanding in comparison to text”. (Ischen et al., 2022, p. 416)	AI modality influences search experience	AI modalities in information search	Information Search and AI Retrieval

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